

Appendix A - Total source population size scenario derivation

Table A.1. The most recent Arctic northern fulmar colony size estimates and projections to 2018 under differing rates of decline.

Source population	colony	year	breeding adults	source	breeding adults in 2018 with -3% per year decline (BBDS rate)	breeding adults in 2018 with -1.5% per year decline (PLI rate)
BBDS	Buchan Gulf	2018	10000	Mallory et al. 2020	--	--
	Scott Inlet	2018	12000	Mallory et al. 2020	--	--
	Qaalluit (Cape Searle)	2018	50000	Mallory et al. 2020	--	--
	Akpait (The Minarets)	1985	30000	Gaston et al. 2006	10980	--
	Exeter Sound	1973	30000	Nettleship et al. 1997	7618	--
LS	Cape Vera	2004	18000	Gaston et al. 2006	11752	14568
	Cape Liddon	2002	14000	Gaston et al. 2006	8600	10992
	Hobhouse Inlet	2001	30000	Gaston et al. 2006	17874	23202
	Prince Leopold Island	2001	32000	Gaston et al. 2006	19066	24750
	Baillarge Bay	2002	40000	Gaston et al. 2006	24570	31408